

Physico-chemical Studies of 1,5-Dimethyl- and 1,5-Diphenyl-1,3,5-pentanetriones with VO(II), Cr(III), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and UO₂(II)[†]

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The compositions of metal complexes formed by 1,5-dimethyl- and 1,5-diphenyl-1,3,5-pentanetriones with VO(II), Cr(III), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and UO₂(II) in dioxan-water mixture (50% v/v) have been determined potentiometrically at 30±0.1° in presence of sodium chloride. It was concluded from this study that 1,5-dimethyl-1,3,5-pentanetrione (H₂DAA) acts as a monobasic and 1,5-diphenyl-1,3,5-pentanetrione (H₂DBA) as a dibasic acid.

THOUGH 1,5-dimethyl-1,3,5-pentanetrione (H₂DAA) was synthesised by Collie *et al*¹ in 1922, not much work has been noticed till 1960. After 1960, β,δ-triketones have been subjected to many investigations. Fernelius *et al*² determined the formation constants of 1-phenyl-1,3,5-hexanetrione and 1,5-diphenyl-1,3,5-pentanetrione with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and UO₂(II) and reported the formation of mononuclear 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. However, Lintvedt and co-workers³⁻⁷ have isolated homobimetallic complexes with H₂DBA with first row transition metal ions. Preliminary studies, of Fernelius appeared to be incorrect, as there are several possibilities through which coordination can occur which may lead to polynuclear complexation. In the present communication we report the compositions and stoichiometries of various metal complexes formed in the aforesaid system.

Experimental

The ligands H₂DAA and H₂DBA were prepared by standard methods^{1,8}. Peroxide-free distilled dioxan was obtained by the literature method⁹. Metal salts (B.D.H., A.R.) solutions were standardised by EDTA¹⁰. Dioxan-water mixture (50% v/v) was prepared by adding 500 ml of deionised water to 500 ml dried and distilled dioxan. This mixture was used for preparing metal salt, ligand and sodium chloride solutions. The ionic strength was maintained constant ($\mu=0.01M$) with sodium chloride solution as mentioned below:

- (i) 0.002M Ligand (10 ml) (*a* or *a'*) + 0.01M NaCl (10 ml) + dioxan-water (30 ml; 50% v/v),
- (ii) 0.002M Ligand (10 ml) (*a* or *a'*) + 0.002M Metal (10 ml) (A-G) + 0.01M NaCl (10 ml) + dioxan-water (20 ml; 50% v/v),

(iii) 0.002M Ligand (15 ml) (*a* or *a'*) + 0.002M Metal (10 ml) (A-G) + 0.01M NaCl (10 ml) + dioxan-water (15 ml, 50% v/v), and

(iv) 0.002M Ligand (20 ml) (*a* or *a'*) + 0.002M Metal (10 ml) (A-G) + 0.01M NaCl (10 ml) + dioxan-water (10 ml; 50% v/v).

(A) denotes VO⁺⁺, (B) Cr⁺⁺⁺, (C) Mn⁺⁺, (D) Co⁺⁺, (E) Ni⁺⁺, (F) Cu⁺⁺, (G) UO₂⁺⁺, *a*, H₂DAA ligand and *a'*, H₂DBA ligand solutions.

Potentiometric titrations were carried out with Digital pH meter (pH-5651 ECIL, Hyderabad) equipped with a combined glass and saturated calomel electrodes. All solutions were thermostated at 30±0.1° prior to titration. The volume of each set of solutions was kept constant (50 ml) as given in systems (i) to (iv) and separately titrated with sodium hydroxide (0.05M) in an oxygen-free nitrogen atmosphere. The change in pH was recorded as a function of volume of [OH⁻] added and graphs were plotted for different sets of solutions.

Results and Discussion

The solutions of the ligands H₂DAA (*a*) and H₂DBA (*a'*) when titrated with NaOH (0.05M) show one inflection corresponding to one and two moles of sodium hydroxide respectively, indicating mono- and dibasic behaviour of *a* and *a'*. Also, H₂DAA is a weaker acid than H₂DBA. The former is therefore expected to form stronger complexes than H₂DBA, with transition metals. The keto and enol forms were recently determined using the nmr¹¹.

In curves A-a, F-a and G-a only one inflection point corresponding to two moles of [OH⁻] at

[†] Dedicated to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra on his sixtieth birthday.

pH 8.0 has been observed when the solution, metal-ligand composition, of (ii) was titrated indicating the presence of $[M(\text{DAA})]$ species (where $M = \text{VO}^{2+}$, Cu^{2+} or UO_2^{2+}). However, with the molecular framework model three or four co-ordinated copper (with one water molecule) with DAA is unlikely as it involves considerable strain, but the species $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{DAA})_2]$ involving square planar structure is more likely. Further in the systems (iii) and (iv) only one inflection corresponding to two moles of $[\text{OH}^-]$ at pH 8.0 was noticed, indicating the formation of aquated $[\text{M}_2(\text{DAA})_2(\text{H}_2\text{DAA})]$ and $[\text{M}(\text{HDAA})_2]$ species, respectively [where $M = \text{VO}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ or $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$]. In all the cases the complex precipitated at $\text{pH} \approx 11.00$.

In case of $\text{Cr}-\text{H}_2\text{DAA}$ system, the curve B-a shows three inflection points corresponding to one, three and four moles of $[\text{OH}^-]$, respectively. The curves also show the liberation of one and three protons from the ligand in the solutions of systems (ii), (iii) and (iv). However, separation of the curves occur only after pH 8 is attained. Liberation of a single proton from the ligand generates the species like $[\text{Cr}(\text{HDAA})]^{2+}$ or $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{HDAA})_2]^{4+}$, while the liberation of three protons accounts for the formation of $[\text{Cr}(\text{DAA})\text{OH}]$ or $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{DAA})_2(\text{OH})_2]$. The liberation of four protons in 1:1 mixture generates anionic complex of the type $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{DAA})_2(\text{OH})_4]^{2-}$. In 2:3 and 1:2 mixtures, nine and five moles of $[\text{OH}^-]$ were consumed, accounting for the formation of $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{DAA})_2(\text{OH})_9]^{3-}$ and $[\text{Cr}(\text{DAA})_2\text{OH}]^{2-}$.

The curve C-a shows some interesting features, as there are two inflection points for each set of compositions. Two inflection points are noted for composition (ii), one at $\text{pH} \approx 9$ and the other at $\text{pH} \approx 11$, corresponding to one and three moles of $[\text{OH}^-]$, respectively. Two complexes $[\text{Mn}(\text{HDAA})_2]$ and the other anionic species $[\text{Mn}(\text{DAA})\text{OH}]^-$ appear to be formed. Further, the curve C-a corresponding to the composition (iii) shows two inflection points at $\text{pH} \approx 9$ and at $\text{pH} \approx 11$ corresponding to 1.5 and 3.5 moles of $[\text{OH}^-]$ pertaining to the neutral $[\text{Mn}_2(\text{HDAA})_2]$ and the anionic species, $[\text{Mn}_2(\text{DAA})_2(\text{OH})]^{2-}$, respectively. In the same curve pertaining to the composition 1:2 two inflection points corresponding to two and four moles of $[\text{OH}^-]$ are noted and the species, $[\text{Mn}(\text{HDAA})_2]$ and $[\text{Mn}(\text{HDAA})_2(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$ are assigned.

The curves D-a and E-a for the composition (ii) show two sharp inflections at $\text{pH} \approx 7$ and ≈ 10 respectively indicating the formation of 1:2 complex $[\text{M}'(\text{HDAA})_2]$ at $\text{pH} \approx 7$ and 1:1 complex $[\text{M}'_2(\text{DAA})_2]$ at $\text{pH} \approx 10$ [$M' = \text{Ni}(\text{II})$ or $\text{Co}(\text{II})$]. It is therefore surprising that Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} prefer to bind with two ligands at lower pH in which each ligand molecule behaves as monobasic ligand. At higher pH the second proton from the ligand is removed forming thereby $[\text{M}'_2(\text{DAA})_2]$. This is contrary to what has been observed for Cu^{2+} . The compositions for the systems (iii) and (iv) show the behaviour similar to Cu^{2+} system, forming the

complexes of the types $[M'_2(DAA).H_2DAA]$ and $[M'(HDAA)_2]$, respectively. In each case two protons were liberated in two different metal-ligand compositions.

The curves A-a' and G-a' show the consumption of five moles of $[OH^-]$, thereby indicating the formation of seven coordinated $[VO(DBA)(OH)_2]^{2-}$ and eight coordinated $[UO_2(DBA)(OH)_3]^{2-}$, respectively. While in systems (iii) and (iv) parallel nature of the curves show that excess of ligand is being titrated.

In the curve B-a' (ii), five moles of $[OH^-]$ have been consumed, indicating thereby the formation of the anionic species, $[Cr(DBA)(OH)_3]^{2-}$. For other metal-ligand composition excess ligand is titrated as indicated by the parallel nature of the curve.

However, in Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} systems, two inflection points in their respective curves (C-a', D-a' and E-a') show two-step complexation. First inflection point between pH 6-9 corresponding to two moles $[OH^-]$, shows the formation of the species $[M(DBA)]$ or $[M_2(DBA)_2]$, which further coordinates to two moles of $[OH^-]$ to form an octahedral homo-bimetallic anionic species of the type $[M(DBA)(OH)_2]^{2-}$ or $[M_2(DBA)_2(OH)_4]^{4-}$ (where $M=Mn^{2+}$, Co^{2+} or Ni^{2+}). The different inflection points for other metal-ligand compositions viz., (iii) and (iv) are, in all the cases, due to the excess of ligand which is being titrated.

Finally in curve F-a' the inflection point for metal-ligand composition (ii) corresponding to four moles of $[OH^-]$ indicate the formation of anionic species $[Cu(DBA)(OH)_2]^{2-}$ or $[Cu_2(DBA)_2(OH)_4]^{4-}$, while in systems (iii) and (iv) the curves are also parallel which indicate that excess of ligand is being titrated.

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